

Industrial Intelligence - Improving Efficiency and Sustainability in Manufacturing

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Abstract

Sustainability imperatives call for fresh approaches to modern machine design. Selecting optimal motion and automation solutions is multifaceted, with no one-size-fits-all answer. Standard pneumatics, electrical automation, and controlled pneumatics each have trade-offs, whereas CO₂ emissions and cost play roles. Guidelines are essential. Leveraging intelligent algorithms and artificial intelligence can reduce CO₂ footprints. As an outlook we touch on emerging fields like biotechnology, which demand scalable automation solutions.

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1 Introduction

Sustainability aspects necessitate a novel approach to modern machine concepts. Selecting the optimal technological solution for motion and automation tasks is multifaceted, and making general assumptions is challenging. Therefore, guidelines are essential. Leveraging intelligent algorithms and artificial intelligence can significantly enhance existing technology in terms of reducing its CO₂ footprint.

Furthermore, emerging application fields such as biotechnology are gaining prominence. Automation technology plays a pivotal role in scaling these applications.

2 Standard Pneumatic, Electrical Automation, and Controlled Pneumatics

Within modern machine concepts, various technological options exist for motion within the machine. These options include standard pneumatics, electrical automation, and controlled pneumatics (i.e., pneumatics supported by proportional valves). Each option has distinct advantages and disadvantages. As a rule of thumb:

- **Pneumatic:** Well-suited for shorter stroke lengths, stronger holding force, and longer holding periods.
- **Electrical automation:** Ideal for longer stroke lengths, weaker holding force, and shorter holding periods.
- **Controlled pneumatics:** Represents a compromise between these two technologies.

However, other factors, such as CO₂ emissions and cost (both initial and total ownership costs), also play a role. Thus, no overarching assumption can be made regarding the superiority of one technology over another. In our discussion, we will provide decision support and highlight the respective sweet spots for each technology.

3 Sustainability and Efficiency in Pneumatics

Improving CO₂ emissions and efficiency in pneumatic systems is achievable. Physics offers a solution: in specific scenarios, expansion energy alone can propel a pneumatic cylinder to its end position without requiring full pressure. This approach can save up to 60% of consumed air and enhance cycle times by nearly 25%. Leveraging

intelligent algorithms and artificial intelligence within the programmable logic controller (PLC) is essential to achieve these savings.

Figure 1: Smart Switching of a Pneumatic Actuator.

Figure 1 illustrates the principle of smart and energy-efficient switching for a pneumatic actuator. The process begins with the PLC sending a signal (1) to open the valve and initiate the air flow. Shortly after (2), the pneumatic actuator starts moving. An AI model, trained specifically for this purpose, identifies the optimal moment (3) when the expansion energy is sufficient to bring the actuator to its end position. At this point, the AI model locks the valve, ensuring efficient operation of the actuator.

4 Outlook – Biotechnology and Biomechanics

The convergence of technology and biology represents one of today's most significant innovations. Numerous applications in pharmaceuticals, food processing, and personalized medicine drive the need for automation technology. Bioreactors play a crucial role in producing medicine, alternative proteins, and personalized meat, highlighting the demand for automation.

There are two current trends for bioreactors: large-scale reactors and small-scale reactors. Large-scale reactors are utilized in pharmaceuticals, green chemistry, alternative proteins and meat products, as well as in reducing CO₂-footprint. Automation potential can be seen in areas such as gas control (N₂, O₂, CO₂), air mass flow controllers, valve manifolds, and shut off valves. Industry 4.0 is also employed to control and optimize continuous processes in large-scale reactors.

On the other hand, small-scale reactors are used in personalized medicine, regenerative medicine, immunotherapy, and tissue engineering. Technologies like mass flow controllers, valve manifolds, pump technology, and cell counting technology are implemented in these systems.

Furthermore, there is a growing trend of completely integrated high throughput systems with multi-parallel bioreactors. These systems also include liquid handling to increase the quantity of production.

Lastly, emerging job profiles like biomechanics combine automation, information technology, and biology, creating new opportunities in this field.